

Copenhagen, 25 March 2026

The table attached to this document specifies the features of the *Listeria* reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB for the Network Laboratories.

The strains are provided as pure cultures in transport media prepared from fresh passages of the reference strains, checked for the specified features. Upon arrival in your laboratory, please prepare a fresh culture for storage in your laboratory. To prepare passages of the strains, use a sterile 1 µl loop to pick part of the culture from the vial and inoculate it in nutrient broth or streak the enrichment culture onto solid agar plates.

A certificate will be provided together with the reference materials.

Please note that the reference strains are provided for being used as positive controls in methods set up, for quality assurance purposes, and specific assays. Any other use or their distribution to other laboratories is not allowed without formal consent from the EURL-PH-FWDB.

BIOSAFETY WARNING

Listeria monocytogenes is a human pathogen that can cause severe invasive disease such as septicaemia and meningitis, particularly in pregnant women, newborns, the elderly, and immunocompromised individuals. Laboratory-acquired infections have been reported. Therefore, it should be handled in accordance with national biosafety guidelines for pathogenic microorganisms, and particular care must be taken when handling pure cultures and materials with high bacterial loads.

Annex 1. List of Listeria reference strains available at the EURL-PH-FWDB

Strain ID	Species	Genotype	Serogroup	Lineage
EURL-LIST-MONO-01	L. monocytogenes	ST9	IIc	II
EURL-LIST-MONO-02	L. monocytogenes	ST8	IIa	II
EURL-LIST-MONO-03	L. monocytogenes	ST2	IVb	I
EURL-LIST-MONO-04	L. monocytogenes	ST7	IIa	II
EURL-LIST-MONO-05	L. monocytogenes	ST1	IVb	I
EURL-LIST-MONO-06	L. monocytogenes	ST1	IVb	I
EURL-LIST-MONO-07	L. monocytogenes	ST6	Ivb	I
EURL-LIST-MONO-08	L. monocytogenes	ST2	Ivb	I